

Meeting Patients with an Interpreter: A Checklist

This checklist aims to enhance the effectiveness of appointments for patients with limited English proficiency who require interpreter support. If the interpreter is in attendance and not on the phone, please verify that they are qualified. This verification should occur at the booking stage and upon the interpreter's arrival. Certified interpreters wear a photo ID card that declares their accreditation with NRPSI.

	Task	Check
Pre-session briefing	1. Explain the aim(s) of the consultation to the interpreter, if known.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	2. If known, brief the interpreter about the health topics to be discussed and clinical procedures to be explained. Give the interpreter time to note down any terminology or concepts that are new to them.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Interaction	3. Introduce you and the interpreter to the patient. Make sure the interpreter sits/stands where it will help you to talk to the patient.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	4. Explain to the patient that the interpreter is bound by a confidentiality agreement and will not discuss the case with anyone external to the consultation.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	5. Expect the consultation to last longer, as everything will be said twice, once by you and once interpreted by the interpreter.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	6. Speak directly to the patient, looking at the patient, not at the interpreter.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	7. Everything you say will be interpreted. Ensure pauses are introduced to allow the interpreter to relay the content. Use simple vocabulary and direct the information to the patient.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	8. Ask the patient to rephrase to confirm they understand your instructions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	9. Do not ask the interpreter for opinions ("Is he telling the truth?"). Interpreters are impartial and cannot express opinions about what you or the patient say.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Post-session briefing	10. If necessary or requested, discuss any issues that may have occurred during the interpreted consultation to avoid them in the future.	<input type="checkbox"/>